

Received-Makale Geliş Tarihi 05.12.2024
Published-Yayınlanma Tarihi 31.01.2025
Volume-Cilt (Issue-Sayı), ss/pp 12 (115), 32-37

Research Article /Araştırma Makalesi
10.5281/zenodo.14787186

Pelin Şahinoğlu

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5947-8696>

Niğde Ömer Halisdemir University, Technical Science and Vocational School, Niğde / TÜRKİYE
ROR Id: <https://ror.org/03ejnre35>

Asst. Prof. Dr. Rüstü Uçan

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2389-8231>

Uskudar University, Faculty of Health Sciences, İstanbul / TÜRKİYE
ROR Id: <https://ror.org/02dzjmc73>

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Müge Ensari Özay

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4785-5503>

Uskudar University, Faculty of Health Sciences, İstanbul / TÜRKİYE
ROR Id: <https://ror.org/02dzjmc73>

Safety Culture Review in the Theme of Management Systems in the Calcite Production Sector-Sample Field Study

Kalsit Üretim Sektöründe Yönetim Sistemleri Temasında, Güvenlik Kültürü İncelemesi- Örnek Saha Çalışması

ABSTRACT

The study aims to examine the safety culture regarding occupational health and safety from the perspective of experts in the calcite production sector. The theme was created with employee work management. Questions suitable for the theme were created after five different expert opinions and one pilot application was made. After the pilot application, the questions were added to the questions to avoid skipping the answers and finalizing. Eight occupational safety experts whose opinions were consulted met the condition of having worked only in calcite production facilities. The views of occupational safety experts working in unrelated sectors were not included. The data obtained using a semi-structured interview technique was analyzed using a guided qualitative analysis technique. The considerations that should be given to sectoral areas under high risk levels were identified. Safety culture has been evaluated from the perspective of sector employees and management. It has been found that establishing a safety culture is more complicated due to the open field studies and the dynamic working environment of the calcite production sector compared to others. Suggestions are presented to overcome this difficulty.

As such, it has been determined that procedures applied without discrimination among individuals and units can give the safety culture permanence. Practices in which only the occupational health and safety department is involved and responsible harm the sustainability of the safety culture. In systems with hands-off management, it becomes challenging to create a safety culture. The present situation can be improved by increasing the frequency of field surveillance. However, it makes sustainability difficult.

When previous studies were examined, no safety culture study based on occupational health and safety related to calcite production facilities was found. For future studies, similar studies in different sectors are thought to contribute to the literature by combining the study with risk parameters. The study is based on an unpublished doctoral thesis.

Keywords: Calcite Sector, Safety culture, Occupational health and safety

ÖZET

Çalışma, kalsit üretim sektöründe çalışan uzmanların bakışı ile iş sağlığı ve güvenliği bakımından güvenlik kültürünü incelemeyi amaçlamaktadır. Çalışan-İş profili-Yönetim ile tema oluşturulmuştur. Temaya uygun sorular, 5 farklı uzman görüşünden sonra oluşturulmuş ve 1 pilot uygulama yapılmıştır. Pilot uygulama sonrası cevapların es geçilmemesi adına sorulara ekleme yapılmış ve son halini almıştır. Görüşüne başvurulmuş 8 iş güvenliği uzmanı, çalışmanın amacına uygun olarak, yalnızca kalsit üretim tesislerinde çalışmış olma şartını sağlamaktadır. Farklı sektörlerde çalışan iş güvenliği uzmanı görüşüne yer verilmemiştir. Yarı- yapılandırılmış görüşme tekniği ile elde edilen veriler, yönlendirilmiş nitel analiz tekniği ile incelenmiştir. Kalsit üretim sektöründe, yüksek risk seviyesine sahip alanlarda nelere dikkat edilmesi gerektiği belirlenmiştir. Güvenlik kültürüne olan bakışım, sektör çalışanlarının ve yönetimin gözünden değerlendirilmesi yapılmıştır. Açık saha çalışmalarında ve dinamik bir çalışma ortamında, güvenlik kültürünün oluşturulmasının diğer sektörlerle göre daha zor olduğu bulunmuş ve bu zorluğun üstesinden gelebilmek için öneriler sunulmuştur. Sonuç olarak, kişi ve birim ayırt edilemsiz uygulanan prosedürlerin, güvenlik kültürünü kalıcı hale getirebileceği saptanmıştır. Yalnızca iş sağlığı ve güvenliği biriminin dahil ve sorumlu olduğu uygulamaların, güvenlik kültürünün sürdürülebilirliğine zarar verdiği görülmüştür. Yönetimin pek fazla dahil olmadığı bir sistemde, güvenlik kültürünü geliştirmek zorlaşmaktadır. Saha gözetimi sıklaştırılarak, mevcut durum iyileştirilebilsede sürdürülebilirlik zorlaşmaktadır.

Önceki çalışmalar incelendiğinde, kalsit üretim tesisleri ile ilgili iş sağlığı ve güvenliği temelinde, güvenlik kültürü çalışmasına rastlanmamıştır. Sonraki çalışmalar için farklı sektörlerde benzer çalışmalar yapılarak literatüre, çalışmanın risk parametreleriyle birleştirilmesiyle sahaya katkı sağlayacağı düşünülmektedir. Çalışma, yayınlanmamış doktora tezinden üretilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Kalsit sektörü, Güvenlik kültürü, İş sağlığı ve güvenliği

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to the nature of the work, open pit mining is one of the higher-risk business lines. And as with all businesses, safety culture plays a critical role in preventing occupational accidents and diseases in mining.

Culture is a concept that is frequently heard and used but often not understood in depth (Özkan and Lajunen, 2003: 3). Safety culture can be defined as a set of perceptions encompassing occupational health and safety rules, which are formed by employees' awareness being influenced by environmental behavior patterns.

Although the terms safety culture and safety climate have different etymological origins, they are often used interchangeably. The definition proposed by the Human Factors Working Group of the Advisory Committee on Safety in Nuclear Installations for the concept of safety climate is as follows: "*The safety culture of an organization is the product of individual and group values, attitude, perceptions, competencies, and patterns of behavior that determine the commitment to, and the style of, an organization's health and safety management.*" While this definition adopts a socio-psychological perspective, it has not led to a general consensus in the literature (Cox and Flin, 1998: 190-191).

The intricacies of the subject are important not only for the employees but also for the sociological basis and economic dimensions of the society. Occupational injuries and accidents concern factors that can be eliminated by taking certain precautions and using appropriate methods (Alli, 2008: 1).

Safety climate refers to the perceived value attached to safety in organizations. Various factors stand out among the essential components of the safety climate. These factors are as follows:

- Management values,
- Management and organizational practices (adequacy of training, provision of safety equipment, quality of safety management systems, etc.),
- Communication and employee involvement in workplace health and safety (Neal et al., 2000: 100).

Research shows that these factors are directly linked to accidents and incidents. In recent years, it has become clear that achieving operational objectives in complex business systems is only possible through sustainable safety-oriented social structures and technical arrangements. A series of major disasters in the past have revealed the critical role played by social and organizational issues in the etiology of these accidents (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD] Nuclear Agency, 1987; Vaughn [1996] as cited in Mearns et. al. 2003: 641; Sheen, 1987).

Elements of safety climate appear in various structural models as predictors of accidents and unsafe behaviors, and the necessity of providing a safe working environment is acknowledged (Thompson et al., 1998: 15; Tomás et al., 1999: 49). Less well known, however, are the antecedent factors that support a favorable safety climate. Hofmann et al. (1995: 139) describe individual attitudes and behaviors in safety climate as micro-level elements of an organization that are shaped by broader safety management systems and practices. In this context, management's attitude and behaviour towards safety spill over to the workforce.

A safe working environment becomes possible when employees understand the impact of the quality of work life on their overall quality of life, reach a sufficient level of awareness on health and safety issues, display a positive attitude that supports a healthy and safe work process, and continue their work in a safety-oriented manner. Safe behavior can only emerge in a work environment where a health and safety culture is established (Şerifoğlu & Sungur, 2007: 3).

Personal protective equipment (PPE) are tools and types of equipment that employees should utilize to protect their health and safety. However, there are cases where employees may refuse to use these equipment. Such situations arise from the society's lack of an adequate safety culture. Notably, in societies where a safety culture is established, the use of PPE is not rejected; on the contrary, employees demand it.

One of the main objectives in business management is to ensure the sustainability of productivity and quality. However, health and safety problems in the workplace can adversely affect the business's productivity. A responsible approach by management, establishing effective procedures, and using modern occupational safety management techniques can reduce accident and injury rates. In addition, a decisive management style will contribute to the adoption of occupational safety culture throughout the organization (Grimald & Simonds, 2001, p. 106).

Therefore, occupational health and safety practices are integral to mining operations. However, no matter how good the technical measures taken are, their successful implementation depends on the willingness of the companies and all employees to create a safety culture.

The establishment of a safety culture in the manner depicted can be sustained primarily by the sensitivity of employers on this issue, and then by the participation of all units in the enterprises. The formation and sustainable maintenance of a safety culture is a balancing work that will yield results over the years. Therefore, talking about the existence of safety culture in enterprises may necessitate examining the changes in that enterprise over the years (Yılmaz, 2022).

According to Wiegman et al. (2002:5), safety culture may show sectoral differences. Many studies deal with safety culture on a sectoral basis, including different sectors such as the chemical, food, and metal industries. This study covers the safety culture in the calcite production sector.

2. METHOD

The study uses qualitative content analysis. The research method was determined as a case study. The data were obtained using semi-structured interviews, which were then analysed using guided qualitative content analysis.

Qualitative Method: It involves in-depth analysis of the events and cases being examined, and interpretation of the emerging meanings (Merriam, 2015). Basically, the qualitative method reveals the meanings that individuals attribute to events and phenomena in their own context (Neuman, 2016). In addition, the qualitative method is recommended in exploratory studies that have not previously been subject to research (Punch, 2016).

A case study is a very suitable method for examining a unique phenomenon, such as a programme, process, institution, process, or social group, in detail (Creswell, 2021). Since only the calcite production sector will be examined, it is the focal point of the study.

Semi-structured interview refers to the fact that the essential questions are prepared in advance but left open-ended to shape the follow-up questions during the interview (Punch, 2016). Unlike the unstructured interview, it is a technique used to obtain and analyze the information relevant to the subject. And unlike the structured interview, it ensures that there is not a single set framework during the interview. It was chosen to be used in our study to be able to add new questions during the interview and to ensure variety in in the offered perspectives (Yılmaz, 2022).

Directed content analysis is defined as the deductive use of theory (Potter & Levine-Donnerstein, 1999). It refers to the creation of themes before analyzing the data and starting the analysis in this context (Kyngas & Vanhanen, 1999).

The study was started by creating a theme, and the interview questions were prepared to be in line with this theme.

Eight experts who worked only in the calcite production sector were subjected to semi-structured interviews. Considering the research's scope, experts working in other sectors were not included. The interviewed experts provided a window to the environment of three different calcite production facilities. The interviews were conducted face-to-face and lasted an average of 25 minutes per person.

The questions were finalized after three revisions and one pilot application by forming a theme from the elements of management systems. In addition to employees and management, a job profile relevant to the study and pertinent to the calcite production facilities was included within the relevant data.

Table 1. Content of the questions for the interview technique

Employee	Employee profile Employee turnover Employees' view of safety culture
Job profile	Sectoral characteristics Differences and similarities with other sectors Causes of accidents in the sector Causes of near misses in the sector
Management	Areas where planning is most necessary Areas where field surveillance is most necessary Areas for improvement Factors complicating security management

Experts were named as E1-E8 according to the order in the interview technique. And the interviews were held between 8.10.2024 and 14.11.2024.

Table 2. Speciality class information and sectoral experience

EXPERT	SECTORAL EXPERIENCE	CERTIFICATE OF EXPERTISE
E1	6 Years	Class A
E2	2 Years	Class A
E3	1 Year	Class C
E4	1 Year	Class C
E5	13 Years	Class A
E6	14 Years	Class A
E7	4 Years	Class A
E8	8 Years	Class B

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Findings related to employee profile

It is concluded that the level of education is at a secondary level in the blue-collar sector. Employee circulation is high, but it is less when compared to the construction sector, and they generally have vocational qualification certificates.

E1:" All of our maintenance workers, maintenance electricians, team electricians, and welders have vocational qualification certificates."

E5" We do not allow anyone without a professional qualification certificate to access all our items here, for example, from the workshop to the mine."

E7 " Generally, we can say that people who do not obey the rules, who need a more comfortable working environment, that is, it would be more accurate to say workshop logic, that is, people who work with the logic of a workshop rather than a production facility."

3.2 Findings related to the employees' perspective on safety culture

The perception of safety culture is not very positive in general. It has been found that blue-collar employees are more work-oriented, and it is difficult, but not impossible, to make changes related to safety culture. While it is more challenging to implement changes in white-collar employees.

E7 "Safety culture is perceived as a process that makes work difficult."

E5 " Safety culture is spreading rapidly. However, it spreads faster in blue-collars."

E4 " We'll give extra training, we'll give it. There is no other way. The employees see the merits our approach after the accident happens. Then they say, "OK, this is really for our sake." They can embrace it that way."

E2 " When there is a lack of field supervision, employees take the easy, erroneous path. This must not be allowed."

E5 " If we are there, there are no mistakes. There is no unsafe work from the employees."

3.3 Managerial perspective on safety culture

It has been concluded that the management's perspective is reflected in the field studies, a positive perspective creates a positive safety culture, and all planning should be done in the direction of integrating management systems.

E7 " One of the biggest problems I see in this sector is that the people above also look at the process this way. They do not care enough about safety culture. This is one of the biggest problems. The whole process should be quality-based, not just production-based. Including occupational safety and the environment."

E2" There should be checklists in every area. All employees should contribute to development. There should be incentives in this direction."

There is a lack of coordination between units in planning. If maintenance-repair is to be carried out, the OHS unit must be informed

E6" Especially training planning should be systematic. Who will participate is very important. Without supervision, the training will be left hanging. This planning should go by days and hours."

3.4 Findings on sectoral accident potential

Improvements in high-risk areas are important to ensure the safety culture sectorally.

E6 " The risk of accidents is very high in all areas from the extraction of the stone in the mountain to the shipment of the product."

E3 " In general, as I said. We need to watch out for blasts in the quarry, while loading the vehicles, especially our trucks, loaders and dust."

E7" The machine production sector is more organized than ours. It is easier to steer in a closed area. There are many processes in the open area. Planning is important. However, the planning we have is production-orientated."

E8 " In general, the areas where the accident potential is high, especially in the open pit operation area, may be effected by the use of construction machinery and mining operations, and the lack of determined traffic rules, speed limit, overloading, and vehicle-pedestrian roads. In the storage areas, accidents may occur due to the irregular, excessive, stacked pile-up of big bags, which weight 1-1.5 tonnes. Also, workers standing high up during the filling and dosing process of bulk calcite or while loading bulk it onto the lorry."

3.5 Factors that make safety management difficult

Lack of coordination between units. The perception that only the occupational safety unit is responsible for safety culture

E3: "If we could involve unit supervisors in the work here, it would be different. It could be better if they also shouldered some of the responsibility."

E7 " employees generally have visual memory. They repeat the wrongs they see from their masters. This is how it keeps going. If the foreman is doing his job well, it is best not to interfere with him too much. Safety culture exists for everyone."

E1 "Other unit supervisors should provide orientation training to their units.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Planning in the sector prioritizes production. This planning creates a concern for blue-collar employees about keeping up with the work and makes it difficult to disseminate the safety culture.

Although blue-collar employees' initial perception of safety culture is not very positive, they can adapt to changes more easily than white-collar employees.

Blasting plans are well conceived. Although blasting is one of the most risky operations, good planning heads off negative results. This shows the importance of planning.

It is concluded that the conditions for obtaining professional qualifications should be improved and that hiring is only appropriate after receiving training in the relevant field.

As a sectoral feature, calcite production facilities have a shift system. The experts did not mention the negative effect of the shift system in terms of safety culture. When asked about risky areas, none of the eight experts did not bring this up as an issue.

In the calcite sector, which has a dynamic system, it is more difficult to plan for and control risk than the sectors operating in closed areas. Work in open pits and blasting process should be planned separately. It is concluded that coordination between units should be ensured by providing operational information such as maintenance and repair to all units through software.

Procedures applied without discriminating between individuals and units can make the security culture prevalent.

Practices in which only the occupational health and safety department is involved and responsible harm the sustainability of the safety culture. In systems with hands-off management, it becomes challenging to create a safety culture. The present situation can be improved by increasing the frequency of field surveillance. However, it makes sustainability difficult.

Since it is a sector where many operations are carried out in open areas, it is more difficult to carry out field surveillance than indoor operations. Maintaining an occupational health and safety conscious environment in which all units are involved, with each unit forming its own team, will reduce the pressure on the occupational safety specialists. Moreover, it will allow them to do their job more efficiently.

REFERENCES

- Alli, B. O. (2008). *Fundamental principles of occupational health and safety* (2nd ed.). International Labour Organization.
- Cox, S., & Flin, R. (1998). Safety culture: philosopher's stone or man of straw? *Work & Stress*, 12 (3), 189–201. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02678379808256861>
- Creswell, J. W. (2021). *Qualitative research methods* (M. Bütün & S. B. Demir, Trans.). Siyasal Kitabevi.
- Grimaldi, J. V., & Simonds, R. H. (2001). *Safety management*. Kartari.
- Hofmann, D. A., Jacobs, R., & Landy, F. (1995). High-reliability process industries: Individual, micro, and macro organizational influences on safety performance. *Journal of Safety Research*, 26 (3), 131-149. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-4375\(95\)00011-E](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-4375(95)00011-E)
- Kyngäs, H., & Vanhanen, L. (1999). Content analysis as a research method. *Hoitotiede*, 11, 3-12.
- Mearns, K., Whitaker, S. M., & Flin, R. (2003). Safety climate, safety management practice and safety performance in offshore environments. *Safety science*, 41(8), 641-680. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-7535\(02\)00011-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-7535(02)00011-5)
- Merriam, S. B. (2015). *A guide to qualitative research design and practice* (S. Turan, Trans.). Nobel Academic Publishing.
- Neal, A., Griffin, M. A., & Hart, P. M. (2000). The impact of organizational climate on safety climate and individual behavior. *Safety Science*, 34(1-3), 99–109. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-7535\(00\)00008-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-7535(00)00008-4)
- Neuman, L. W. (2016). *Social research methods: Quantitative and qualitative approaches II* (Ö. Akkaya, Trans.). Publishing Room.
- OECD Nuclear Agency, (1987). Chernobyl and the Safety of Nuclear Reactors on OECD Countries. Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, Paris.
- Özkan, T., & Lajunen, T. (2003). Safety culture and climate. *Pivolka*, 2(10), 3-4.
- Potter, W., & Levine-Donnerstein, D. (1999). Rethinking validity and reliability in content analysis. *Journal of Applied Communication Research*, 27, 258-284. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00909889909365539>
- Punch, K. F. (2016). *Introduction to social research* (D. Bayrak, H. B. Arslan, & Z. Akyüz, Trans.). Siyasal Kitabevi.
- Sheen, B., & Great Britain. Department of Transport. (1987). MV Herald of Free Enterprise: report of Court no. 8074; formal investigation. H.M.S.O.
- Şerifoğlu, U. K., & Sungur, E. (2007). Establishment of health and safety culture in enterprises: The role of top management and the use of in-house communication opportunities. *Istanbul University Institute of Business Economics Management Journal*, 18(58), 1-17.
- Thompson, R. C., Hilton, T. F., & Witt, L. A. (1998). Where the safety rubber meets the shop floor: A confirmatory model of management influence on workplace safety. *Journal of Safety Research*, 29(1), 15–24. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4375\(97\)00033-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4375(97)00033-X)
- Tomás, J. M., Melia, J. L., & Oliver, A. (1999). A cross-validation of a structural equation model of accidents: Organisational and psychological variables as predictors of work safety. *Work & Stress*, 13(1), 49-58. <https://doi.org/10.1080/026783799296156>
- Wiegman, D. A., Zhang, H., Thaden, T. V., Sharma, G., & Mitchell, A. (2002). A synthesis of safety culture and safety climate research. *Technical Report*. http://www.aviation.illinois.edu/avimain/papers/research/pub_pdfs/techreports/02-03.pdf
- Yılmaz, C. (2022). Analyzing occupational health and safety education in the context of adult learning theories: qualitative case study. [Unpublished doctoral thesis]. Sakarya University.